

Comparing Normalizing Flows with Kernel Density Estimation in Estimating Risk of Automated Driving Systems

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Abstract—The development of safety validation methods is essential for the safe deployment and operation of Automated Driving Systems (ADSs). One of the goals of safety validation is to prospectively evaluate the risk of an ADS dealing with real-world traffic. Scenario-based assessment is a widely-used approach, where test cases are derived from real-world driving data. To allow for a quantitative analysis of the system performance, the exposure of the scenarios must be accurately estimated. The exposure of scenarios at parameter level is expressed using a Probability Density Function (PDF). However, assumptions about the PDF, such as parameter independence, can introduce errors, while avoiding assumptions often leads to oversimplified models with limited parameters to mitigate the curse of dimensionality.

This paper considers the use of Normalizing Flows (NF) for estimating the PDF of the parameters. NF are a class of generative models that transform a simple base distribution into a complex one using a sequence of invertible and differentiable mappings, enabling flexible, high-dimensional density estimation without restrictive assumptions on the PDF's shape. We demonstrate the effectiveness of NF in quantifying risk and risk uncertainty of an ADS, comparing its performance with Kernel Density Estimation (KDE), a traditional methods for non-parametric PDF estimation. While NF require more computational resources compared to KDE, NF is less sensitive to the curse of dimensionality. As a result, NF can improve risk uncertainty estimation, offering a more precise assessment of an ADS's safety.

This work illustrates the potential of NF in scenario-based safety. Future work involves experimenting more with using NF for scenario generation and optimizing the NF architecture, transformation types, and training hyperparameters to further enhance their applicability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Automated Driving Systems (ADSs) are expected to improve traffic safety, comfort, and congestion by reducing human errors [1]. While lower-level systems like adaptive cruise control and lane keeping assist are already common, higher-level ADSs (SAE Level 3 and 4) are nearing large-scale deployment. Ensuring their safety prior to release is critical. As large-scale road testing is impractical [2], prospective methods are required. Scenario-based safety validation has emerged as a widely supported approach in the automotive domain [3, 4].

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An essential aspect of scenario-based safety validation is risk estimation, where risk is the combination of exposure to a scenario and the consequence of the response to that scenario. A Probability Density Function (PDF) measures the exposure to different scenarios at the parameter level. However, making assumptions about the PDF, e.g., assuming parameter independence, can introduce errors. Conversely, avoiding such assumptions often results in oversimplified models that include only a limited number of parameters to address the curse of dimensionality.

Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) [5, 6] is a non-parametric method for estimating the PDF that does not rely on assumptions regarding the shape of the PDF. In the literature, KDE has been utilized to estimate the PDF of scenario parameters for the assessment of ADSs [7, 8]. However, a notable disadvantage of KDE is its susceptibility to the curse of dimensionality. As an alternative, this paper explores the use of Normalizing Flows (NF) [9], another non-parametric method for PDF estimation, which has demonstrated promising results for high-dimensional data.

In this work, we will compare the use of KDE and NF in estimating the exposure of scenarios at the parameter level and the associated risk estimated using scenarios sampled from the estimated PDFs. To the best of our knowledge, NF have not been utilized in the literature on safety assessment methods for ADSs. Furthermore, several recent survey papers on scenario generation [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15] do not mention the application of NF. Consequently, this study aims to provide an initial perspective on the potential of NF for the safety assessment of ADSs. Specifically, this work will address two different aspects of safety assessment. The first part involves comparing the use of NF and KDE in estimating the PDF of scenario parameters, leading to the following research question:

Research question 1. *How do NF and KDE compare in estimating the PDF of scenario parameters?*

The second aspect focuses on comparing NF and KDE in estimating the risk, following the procedure outlined in [7]. Thus, the second research question is:

Research question 2. *When used for scenario exposure modeling, how do NF and KDE compare in quantifying ADS risk?*

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the risk quantification method.

This work is structured as follows. Section II first briefly explains the risk quantification method of [7], after which we explain how NF and KDE are exploited in this paper. In Section III-A, the case study is first detailed, after which the results aiming to answer the aforementioned research questions are presented. This work concludes with a discussion in Section IV and conclusions and a future outlook in Section V.

II. METHOD

This section first clarifies how we quantify the risk of an ADS. This also shows that a PDF is needed to estimate the exposure of scenarios at parameter level. Since the shape of the PDF is generally unknown beforehand, we propose to use a non-parametric method for estimating the PDF. This work employs NF for non-parametric PDF estimation and compares this with the more traditional KDE. Section II-B explains NF and how this work utilizes them and Section II-C provides further details on KDE.

A. Risk quantification

As explained in [7] and in line with the ISO 26262 standard [16], risk consists of three components: exposure, severity, and controllability (definitions are in [7, 16]). When calculating severity, the extent of harm in a potential collision should be considered. For the sake of comparing NF with KDE, however, this work treats all collisions equally. Thus, we will express the risk as the probability of a collision given that the ADS deals with a certain predefined type of scenario. Fig. 1 summarizes the risk quantification approach that is used in this work.

Let $R(x)$ denote the simulation outcome of a scenario that is parameterized by $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$. If $R(x) = 1$ denotes a simulation run that ends in a crash and $R(x) = 0$ otherwise, then $\mathbb{E}[R(x)]$ is the expected probability of a collision, which is what we aim to estimate. To estimate this, we need to know how x is distributed. As the underlying PDF of x is generally unknown, this needs to be estimated. For this, we will use either NF (Section II-B) or KDE (Section II-C). For now, we assume that the PDF denoted by p_x , is known and that sampling from the PDF is possible. A straightforward way to estimate $\mathbb{E}[R(x)]$ is using a crude Monte Carlo simulation:

$$\mathbb{E}[R(x)] = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} R(x)p_x(x) dx \quad (1)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{N_{MC}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{MC}} R(x_k), \quad x_k \sim p_x, \quad (2)$$

where N_{MC} denotes the number of simulation runs.

In practice, the expected probability of a collision is low. As a result, many simulations are required to obtain enough confidence in (2). To accelerate the evaluation, importance sampling is utilized [7]. With importance sampling, we sample from the importance density, p_x^* , instead of sampling from p_x . To acquire an unbiased estimate of $\mathbb{E}[R(x)]$, the simulation results are weighted to correct for the fact that we sample from p_x^* instead of p_x :

$$\mathbb{E}[R(x)] \approx \frac{1}{N_{NIS}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{NIS}} R(x_k) \frac{p_x(x_k)}{p_x^*(x_k)}, \quad x_k \sim p_x^*, \quad (3)$$

where N_{NIS} denotes the number of simulation runs with importance sampling.

Ideally, p_x^* is chosen such that the estimation error of (3) is minimized. However, this requires the value of $\mathbb{E}[R(x)]$ and a functional form of $R(x)$; both are unavailable. Therefore, we will follow the approach in [7] and first conduct the crude Monte Carlo sampling and determine p_x^* on the results thereof. More specifically, we select the N_C most critical scenarios, where the criticality of a simulated scenario is based on the minimum time to collision. Since the N_C most critical scenarios is a subset of the N_{MC} scenarios, $N_C < N_{MC}$. Note that the time-to-collision is an appropriate metric for the scenario considered in our case study [17] (Section III), but this might not be an appropriate metric to measure the criticality in simulations of other type of scenarios. Based on those N_C scenarios, p_x^* is constructed with KDE, which is explained in Section II-C. KDE is preferred over NF for constructing the importance density due to its computational simplicity. Moreover, while KDE may result in a less optimal approximation of $\mathbb{E}[R(x)]$ in terms of the uncertainty, we will demonstrate and discuss in the results that it exhibits a lower risk of introducing bias in the estimate of $\mathbb{E}[R(x)]$.

B. Normalizing flows

NF offer a flexible, deep-learning-based method capable of modeling complex, high-dimensional distributions. NF are a class of generative models that estimate complex probability distributions by transforming a simple base distribution through a sequence of invertible and differentiable mappings [18].

Where p_x denotes the unknown PDF of x , let $p_z : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a known and tractable density of a random variable with realization $z \in \mathbb{R}^d$. A typical choice for p_z is the standard Gaussian distribution. The main idea of NF is to estimate a transformation function $f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, parameterized by θ ,

such that $x = f_\theta(z)$. Now, we can compute the PDF of x using the change of variables formula [9]:

$$p_x(x) = p_z(f_\theta^{-1}(x)) \left| \det \left(\frac{\partial f_\theta^{-1}(x)}{\partial x} \right) \right| \quad (4)$$

where the magnitude of the determinant of the Jacobian, $\left| \det \left(\frac{\partial f_\theta^{-1}(x)}{\partial x} \right) \right|$, ensures that the requirements of a density are maintained after applying the transformation f_θ^{-1} . To ensure that (4) is tractable, the transformation f_θ must be easy to invert and its Jacobian must be easy to compute. An important point, as noted in [19], is that if two transformations h and g have these two properties, then so has their composition $g \circ h$. Thus, the transformation f_θ can be made deeper by composing multiple instances of it with different parameters θ .

In this work, the following implementation of NF is adopted. A composition of four transformation functions is used, where each transformation function is a coupling layer, consisting of:

- A Masked Autoregressive Flow (MAF) layer [19], where a residual network with two pre-activation residual blocks are used with each MAF [20]. We opted to use this type of transformer due to its simplicity and sufficiency for our purposes, making more complex alternatives unnecessary in this context. Each block uses two masked dense layers with $2d$ hidden features each. During training, a dropout rate of 20% is used.
- A batch normalization layer to improve optimization [21].
- A random permutation matrix fixed at the start of the training. This is necessary because the MAF layer leaves part of the input unchanged. That is also why at least three coupling layers are necessary, while at least four are preferred [22].

As the base distribution, we use a standard d -dimensional Gaussian distribution with zero mean and an identity matrix as variance. During training, 80% of the available data is used to optimize the transformation parameters θ . The remaining 20% is used to test how well the estimation performs. We employed the Adam optimizer [23], a widely-used, first-order, gradient-based optimization algorithm implemented in PyTorch. A maximum of 5000 iterations are used during optimization, but if the performance is not improving over 100 iterations, the optimization is terminated. This whole procedure is repeated four times with different initializations of θ . Then, θ is based on the best performance during the different iterations.

C. Kernel density estimation

KDE [5, 6] is widely used due to its simplicity and ability to approximate arbitrary distributions without assuming an underlying parametric model. Given a set of N scenario parameters observed in data, $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$, KDE estimates the density at x by averaging kernel functions K centered around each data point:

$$p_x(x) = \frac{1}{Nh^d} \sum_{i=1}^N K \left(\frac{1}{h}(x - x_i) \right), \quad (5)$$

where h is the bandwidth parameter that controls the level of smoothing. The choice of h is crucial — too small a bandwidth leads to overfitting, while too large a bandwidth oversmooths the PDF estimate. A common method for determining h is leave-one-out cross-validation because this minimizes the difference between the real PDF and the estimated PDF according to the Kullback-Leibler divergence [24]. Commonly used kernel functions include Gaussian, Epanechnikov, and uniform kernels [25]. The choice of the Kernel function, K , is commonly considered less important than the bandwidth.

In this paper, we will adopt the often-used Gaussian kernel. For the bandwidth selection, leave-one-out cross-validation is used because of the aforementioned reason.

III. CASE STUDY

This section explains the case study that has been conducted in order to answer the research questions discussed in the introduction. Section III-A explains how the case study has been conducted. In Section III-B, results related to Research question 1 are discussed. Section III-C aims to provide an answer to Research question 2.

A. Setup case study

To demonstrate the use of NF and KDE for quantifying the risk, we will estimate the risk of a collision for a driver model based on the Fuzzy Safety Model (FSM) [26]. We have chosen the FSM because it has successfully been used to provide a benchmark for ADSs [26]. The FSM uses two surrogate safety metrics for rear-end collision, the proactive fuzzy safety and critical fuzzy safety [27]. The vehicle will start to gently brake as soon as the former is nonzero, while heavier braking will start as soon as the latter becomes nonzero.

For the risk quantification, this paper considers cut-in scenarios. In these scenarios, another vehicle is driving in the lane next to the ego vehicle while initiating a lane change towards the lane of the ego vehicle. After the lane change, the other vehicle becomes the leading vehicle of the ego vehicle. The scenarios are parameterized using four parameters:

- 1) the initial longitudinal velocity of the ego vehicle;
- 2) the longitudinal velocity of the other vehicle, which is assumed to be constant throughout the scenario;
- 3) the initial lateral velocity of the other vehicle, which is assumed to be constant until the vehicle completed its lane change, after which the lateral velocity becomes zero; and
- 4) the distance between the ego vehicle and the other vehicle at the start of the scenario.

To obtain realistic parameter values, cut-in scenarios are extracted from the HighD dataset [28]. The approach presented in [29] has been used to extract scenarios from a dataset, while [30] provide more specific details on how scenarios are extracted from the HighD dataset. In total, 2916 cut-in scenarios are collected for this work's case study.

To study the influence of the amount of data, the experiments are repeated for various amount of data. Initially, only 10% of the data are used (292 cut-in scenarios) and the amount

Fig. 2. Mean log-likelihood of the samples that are not used for fittings the PDF. The solid lines show the median of the 50 repetitions, while the colored areas denote the Inter-Quartile Range (IQR).

of data is gradually increased. Selection of the samples is done without replacement, so a single data entry is used at most once during a single experiment. To reduce the impact of randomness, for each selected data size, the experiments are repeated 50 times.

B. Answering research question 1

To answer Research question 1, Fig. 2 shows the mean log-likelihood of the samples that are not used for fitting the PDF. The mean log-likelihood is a measure of how well a PDF explains observed data. Mathematically, if $\{x_j\}_{j \in I_{\text{test}}}$ with I_{test} denotes the set of indices of the scenario parameter vectors that are not used for fitting the PDF, then the mean log-likelihood is

$$\frac{1}{\text{card}(I_{\text{test}})} \sum_{j \in I_{\text{test}}} \log p_x(x_j). \quad (6)$$

Here, $\text{card}(I_{\text{test}})$ denotes the cardinality of I_{test} and equals the number of scenarios that are not used for fitting the PDF. In addition, in (6), the estimated PDF is used for p_x . The solid lines in Fig. 2 show the medians over the 50 repetitions, while the colored area denote the Inter-Quartile Range (IQR). We prefer the median and IQR over the mean and standard deviation, as they are less sensitive to the influence of outliers.

Fig. 2 shows that both NF and KDE perform better if more data are used. This result can be expected, as the use of more data generally results in better fits. Fig. 2 also shows that NF mostly outperforms KDE. Only when using 10% of the data, KDE scores slightly better than NF when considering the median. When using more than 30% of the data, the IQR of NF is entirely above the IQR of KDE, indicating that NF provide a significantly better fit of the PDF.

For quantifying the risk, a good approximation p_x^* of the entire domain \mathbb{R}^d is not important. Rather, as can be seen in (1), all that matters is a good approximation of p_x^* for the values of x where $R(x) = 1$. For a good ADS, it can be expected that collisions are rare, such that $R(x) = 1$ only when x is near the boundary. Hence, we are interested in how NF and KDE compare in estimating the PDF of the scenario parameters near the boundaries. For this, we have evaluated

Fig. 3. Similar to Fig. 2, but now only the samples at the Pareto front are considered for calculating the mean log-likelihood.

the mean log-likelihood of (6) with I_{test} replaced by I_{pareto} , where I_{pareto} denotes the indices of the scenarios that are at the Pareto front of the remaining scenarios. Thus,

$$I_{\text{pareto}} = \{j \in I_{\text{test}} : \{j' \in I_{\text{test}} : x_{j'} \succ x_j\} = \emptyset\} \cup \{j \in I_{\text{test}} : \{j' \in I_{\text{test}} : x_j \succ x_{j'}\} = \emptyset\}$$

where $x_{j'} \succ x_j$ indicates that all d entries of $x_{j'}$ are strictly larger than the corresponding entries of x_j .

Fig. 3 shows the mean log-likelihoods for the NF and KDE when only considering the scenario parameters that are at the Pareto front. Whereas NF outperforms KDE in Fig. 2, now KDE generally provides equal or better scores. Especially when using 40% or less data, KDE provides higher likelihoods, which is significant according to the Mann-Whitney U test. When using more than 40%, NF and KDE perform approximately similar.

In conclusion, NF perform significantly better in estimating the PDF of the scenario parameters compared to KDE (see Fig. 2). However, when considering the extreme values of the scenario parameters, KDE performs significantly better than NF if only 40% or less data is used, while with more data, KDE and NF perform similar (see Fig. 3).

C. Answering research question 2

Fig. 4 shows the estimated collision probability using (3) with $N_{\text{NIS}} = N_{\text{MC}} = 10000$ while using different amounts of data. Clearly, the estimated collision probability is substantially higher if KDE is used compared to NF. On average, with KDE, the estimated collision probability is roughly 40 times higher (note the log scale in Fig. 4). As no ground truth is available, we cannot argue that one approach is better. It might be argued that NF assigns too little probability mass to the tails of the distribution [31]. However, especially when using at least 40% of the data, NF do not perform worse in terms of the mean log-likelihood of the extreme values as we have seen in Fig. 3. In addition, it might be argued that KDE overestimates the probability density near the tails of the distribution [32].

Fig. 4 shows that the estimated collision probability decreases with the use of more data. For KDE, this effect has

Fig. 4. Estimated collision risk using (3). The solid lines show the median of the 50 repetitions, while the colored areas denote the Inter-Quartile Range (IQR).

already been explained in [8]: with less data, the bandwidth used for the KDE tends to be larger, leading to larger tails of the estimated PDF. Since the collisions occur at the tails of the distribution, this also leads to an overestimation. Although NF assign substantially less mass to the probability density near the tails, resulting in a lower estimated probability collision, a similar effect can be observed.

The IQRs in Fig. 4 show that the variance of the results with NF is relatively larger compared to KDE. In absolute terms, however, the IQR for KDE is larger (note the log scale). Both results are not unexpected: when estimating a smaller probability, the uncertainty scales roughly with the square root of this probability, meaning that the IQR will be smaller with smaller medians and that the ratio of IQR and the median will increase with smaller estimations. However, when a large part of the data is used, the IQR with KDE gets significantly smaller. When using all data, the IQR with KDE is almost zero. This can be explained from the fact that when using all data, this results in 50 times the same result PDF estimation with KDE, since KDE is fully deterministic. Thus, the only difference in the 50 repetitions comes from the crude Monte Carlo and importance sampling, which only contribute little to the overall variance, as already observed in [8]. For NF, however, the PDF estimations still vary due to the random initializations of the NF, as during the 50 repetitions, a different seed has been used for initializing the NF before training.

In conclusion, the results of the estimated collision probability differ substantially when using NF or KDE (see Fig. 4). When using NF, the estimated collision probability is an order of magnitude lower. An explanation for this outcome is that KDE generally assigns more probability mass to the tails of the PDF estimation and the collisions occur at these tails of the PDF.

IV. DISCUSSION

This paper’s objective was to compare NF with KDE in estimating the PDF of scenario parameters and compare the estimated ADS risk with these estimated PDFs. The results

show that NF generally provide significantly better estimations of the PDF, while at the extremes of the data, the differences are more subtle with KDE performing better than NF with low amounts of training data and equal performance otherwise. When estimating the risk, it appears that the estimated risk is substantially higher when KDE is used. A possible explanation is that KDE overestimates the probability density near the tails of the distribution [32] and as a result, a higher collision probability is estimated. Besides these findings, there may be other reasons to prefer NF over KDE or vice versa, which are further discussed in this section.

As discussed in Section II-A, for determining the importance density p_x^* , KDE has been used, also if NF has been used for estimating p_x . The reason for this is that we prefer an importance density that is larger than the ideal importance density at the tails, rather than an importance density for which $p_x^* \ll R(x)p_x(x)$. As can be seen from (3), if the latter is the case, this would either lead to a high variance in the outcome, or in a biased outcome since we would not sample values of x where $p_x^* \ll R(x)p_x(x)$. Given that KDE generally overestimates the tails, it might result in a slower convergence, but we compensated this with a rather large number of simulations. Note that with longer simulation times or higher dimensional scenario parameter vectors, NF might be preferred to estimate p_x^* .

In general, KDE suffer from the curse of dimensionality [33], while NF scale better with higher dimensions [18]. Thus, when providing higher-dimensional data, NF may be preferred. In this study, we have applied KDE and NF on $d = 4$ -dimensional data. Therefore, we have not explored the potential of NF with higher-dimensional data. In a future publication, we will study the use of NF for the assessment of ADSs when using higher-dimensional data, which enables to capture more details of the scenarios with the scenario parameters.

Another consideration is computational speed. For fitting the PDF, KDE is generally faster than NF, which require substantial training time. Computational speed was not the primary focus of this study, so only limited conclusions can be drawn. However, fitting the KDE on the full dataset took approximately 1.6s, whereas with NF, it required around 95s, making it roughly 60 times slower. Even with complex bandwidths, such as a full-rank bandwidth matrix, KDE is likely to remain more efficient. However, the computational speed for evaluating the PDF varies. For NF, it depends on model complexity, while for KDE, it depends on the number of samples used. With small datasets, KDE may evaluate densities faster than NF, but this advantage diminishes as the dataset size increases.

The last consideration we will discuss is ease of use. KDE is more straightforward to implement. While NF may potentially offer superior PDF estimation, their performance depends on various choices, including the choice of architecture (e.g., number and size of layers), types of transformations, and optimization hyperparameters. Therefore, if ease of use is a priority, KDE is the preferable option.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study compared Normalizing Flows (NF) and Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) in the context of risk quantification for Automated Driving Systems (ADSs). Our findings show that NF outperform KDE in estimating the Probability Density Function (PDF) of the scenario parameters. KDE, while simpler and computationally more efficient to train, tends to overestimate probability density in the tails, which can lead to higher risk estimations.

Future work will explore the application of NF for scenario generation, particularly for modeling more complex scenarios involving a larger number of parameters. Additionally, we aim to investigate how different NF architectures, transformation strategies, and training procedures affect performance in terms of accuracy and computational cost. Another topic for future research is the comparison of NF and KDE with other density estimators like variational autoencoders [34] and diffusion models [35]. In this way, we seek to improve the overall robustness of scenario-based safety assessment frameworks for ADSs.

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